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EABA INFORMATION PAPER

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Standards and Guidelines for Algae LCAs

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a crucial tool to evaluate the environmental impacts of products and systems, including algae-based products and algae production and processing facilities. To conduct meaningful LCA studies, practitioners must navigate a complex framework of standards, guidelines, and initiatives. This information paper provides a concise overview of these resources, clarifying their roles and interrelationships. Standards, such as the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14040 and 14044, alongside the European Standard EN 17983, establish the foundational principles and requirements for algae LCAs, ensuring consistency and comparability across studies. Complementing these, guidelines such as the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) introduced by the European Commission, the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook, and Publicly Available Specification (PAS) 2050 deliver practical instructions to implement these standards effectively.

In addition, projects and initiatives such as ALIGNED (“Aligning life cycle assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance”) and LCA4BIO (“Harmonised life cycle assessment methods for sustainable and circular bio-based systems”) promote methodological innovation and sector-specific alignment (or harmonisation) by addressing emerging challenges and enhancing collaboration. Understanding the complementary functions of these standards, guidelines, and initiatives enables practitioners to produce scientifically robust and transparent algae LCAs aligned with best international practices. This information paper serves as a foundational resource for selecting and applying the most appropriate frameworks and tools in algae LCA studies.

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OPENING REMARKS

WHY THIS PAPER?

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is the main tool used to evaluate the environmental impacts of algae-based products. However, the large number of available standards and guidelines can make it difficult to decide which ones to follow when conducting an LCA study. Most practitioners rely on EN ISO 14040 and 14044, the core international standards for product LCAs, but several other documents (general, sector-specific, and algae-focused) also offer valuable guidance. This paper clarifies the overall landscape of standards, guidelines, and initiatives, summarises their scope, and shows how they complement the ISO framework.

HOW DO ALGAE LCAs CONNECT TO EXISTING STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES?

Algae LCAs connect to existing standards and guidelines by recognising algae's dual role as both a bio-based product and a feedstock for a wide range of industrial applications, including food and feed ingredients, biofertilisers, cosmetic products etc. This multifaceted nature provides the overarching rationale for applying a layered system of standards and guidelines. First, core LCA principles are governed by internationally recognised standards, such as EN ISO 14040 and 14044, which establish the fundamental structure, requirements, and transparency mandates for conducting LCA studies. Second, because algae are considered a bio-based product, their cultivation and processing stages are subject to relevant standards that apply across the broader bioeconomy. These include standards addressing biomass sustainability, resource efficiency, and methodologies for accounting for biogenic carbon as well as land and water use. For instance, when algae are used in biofuel production, the applied LCA methodology must align with specific sustainability criteria, often involving standards related to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions accounting. Third, the diversity of algae-based applications necessitates the use of standards from related industrial sectors. For instance, when algae systems integrate Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU), practitioners can draw on methodologies from existing CCU and industrial symbiosis frameworks. Similarly, when producing high-value biochemicals, LCAs may reference relevant standards for chemical production to address specific toxicity and end-of-life considerations. Together, this alignment with multiple layers of standards – from core LCA to bio-based sector and application-specific guidelines – enables practitioners to apply a consistent, transparent, and scientifically robust approach that accurately captures the complex environmental impacts of algae systems across their entire value chain.

WHO IS THIS INFORMATION PAPER FOR?

This information paper is intended for both industrial stakeholders and academic researchers who conduct and interpret algae LCAs. It supports anyone aiming to improve the comparability and consistency of their studies by selecting the most relevant standards and guidelines.

WHAT TO EXPECT FROM THIS INFORMATION PAPER?

This paper provides a rationale for selecting appropriate standards and guidelines for algae LCAs. It outlines the scope and key content of the most relevant documents for conducting and interpreting LCA studies of algae systems, with particular attention to several algae-specific standards and guidelines.

ABBREVIATIONS

BECCS – BioEnergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
BSI – British Standards Institution
CDM – Clean Development Mechanism
CEN – European Committee for Standardization
CFP – Carbon Footprint Product
CCU – Carbon Capture and Utilisation
EC – European Commission
EN – European Norm
EPD – Environmental Product Declaration
EU – European Union
GHG – Greenhouse Gas
ILCD – International Life Cycle Data
ISO – International Organization for Standardization
JRC – Joint Research Center
LCA – Life Cycle Assessment
LCI – Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA – Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MCFS – Microalgae Carbon Fixation and Sinking
PAS – Publicly Available Specification
PEF – Product Environmental Footprint
PCR – Product Category Rules
SBTi – Science-Based Target initiative
SDGs – Sustainable Development Goals
SETAC – Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
S-LCA – Social Life Cycle Assessment
TFS – Together For Sustainability
TC – Technical Committee
UNEP – United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WBCSD – World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WRI – World Resources Institute

INTRODUCTION

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a crucial tool for evaluating the environmental impacts of products, processes, and systems, including emerging sectors such as algae-based industries. To ensure scientific robustness, comparability, and credibility, practitioners rely on a comprehensive framework of standards, guidelines, and initiatives. Together, these resources provide the methodological foundation, operational guidance, and sector-specific insights necessary for conducting rigorous assessments.

The landscape of LCA resources is diverse and multilayered, encompassing formal standards, technical guidelines, and collaborative initiatives. Standards, such as EN ISO 14040 and 14044, are internationally recognised documents that establish the requirements and principles for algae LCA. They are often contractually or technically binding in many contexts, providing the foundational rules for conducting assessments. Guidelines, such as the PEF, ILCD Handbook, and PAS 2050, offer detailed operational guidance to supplement these standards. They provide practical, step-by-step instructions to help practitioners implement standards effectively. Initiatives and projects, such as ALIGNED and LCA4BIO, focus on harmonisation, innovation, and sector-specific advancements, often filling gaps where formal standards and guidelines may not yet exist.

While these resources are complementary, they differ in authority, scope, and application. Standards provide the binding framework for LCA, guidelines offer practical support for implementation, and initiatives drive ongoing improvements and sector-specific solutions.

This paper provides an overview of the LCA landscape for algae systems, structured as follows:

- 1. International and European standards:** Formal standards that define core principles and requirements for LCA, including algae-specific standards.
- 2. Guidelines and sector-specific documents:** Technical and sector-specific guidance that supplements standards with operational details and best practices.
- 3. Past and ongoing initiatives:** Collaborative projects driving harmonisation and innovation in LCA methodologies for algae and bio-based systems.

1. INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN STANDARDS RELEVANT TO ALGAE LCAs

This section outlines the international and European standards relevant to algae LCAs, including both algae-specific and more generic LCA standards. These standards provide a robust framework for conducting transparent, consistent, and comparable LCA studies and are summarised in Table 1.

1.1. EN ISO 140X: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

1.1.1. EN ISO 14040 AND EN ISO 14044: CORE PRINCIPLES AND FRAMEWORK

EN ISO 14040 and 14044 are the foundational international standards for life cycle assessment, establishing the principles, framework, and requirements for conducting LCA studies. Developed by ISO Technical Committee 207 on Environmental Management, these standards provide the methodological backbone for LCA practices worldwide, despite occasional criticism regarding their generic nature.

These standards define over 40 essential terms, including life cycle assessment, product, process, and cut-off criteria. However, they do not explicitly address terms such as greenhouse gas emissions or carbon footprint (CFP), which are covered in more specialised standards (e.g., ISO 14067). EN ISO 14040 and 14044 intentionally allow practitioners flexibility in methodological choices, such as defining the functional unit, system boundaries, method to handle multifunctionality, cut-off rules, and impact categories. While this flexibility facilitates adaptability, it also highlights the need for sector-specific guidance to ensure consistency, transparency, and comparability across studies.

First published in 1997, EN ISO 14040 remains the fundamental standard for LCA. It provides practitioners with definitions and requirements for improving the environmental performance of products throughout their life cycle. The standard supports strategic planning, priority setting, product or process design and redesign, and marketing applications, such as ecolabelling, environmental claims, or Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs). EN ISO 14040 is not intended for contractual or regulatory purposes but is typically applied alongside EN ISO 14044, which offers detailed procedural requirements for conducting LCAs.

EN ISO 14044, originally published as three separate standards (EN ISO 14041, 14042, and 14043), consolidates the requirements and guidelines for all phases of an LCA study. This includes goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), life cycle interpretation, and reporting to both the study's commissioner and third parties. The standard also addresses comparative assertions intended for public disclosure and the critical review process, ensuring rigor and transparency in LCA studies.

Other guidelines provide more prescriptive guidance, including the EU Recommendation 2021/2279 on the Product Environmental Footprint, the ILCD Handbook, PAS 2050, and the GHG Protocol, reinforcing their central role in LCA methodology.

Fig.1 - Improved transparency, reproducibility, and comparability in life cycle assessment studies of algae-based products.

1.1.2. ISO 14075: SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

ISO 14075 introduces a structured framework for social life cycle assessment (S-LCA), guiding practitioners through the evaluation of social impacts across a product's life cycle. The standard provides detailed guidance on goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation, enabling transparent evaluation of labor conditions, human rights, and community well-being. By aligning with international conventions, ISO 14075 supports organisations in measuring, communicating, and improving their social sustainability performance, complementing the environmental focus of EN ISO 14040 and 14044.

1.2. EN ISO 1406X: CARBON FOOTPRINT AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY STANDARDS

The EN ISO 1406x series of standards, developed by ISO Technical Committee 207, Subcommittee 7 on Environmental Management, focuses on GHG management, carbon footprint quantification, and climate neutrality. Among these, EN ISO 14067 and EN ISO 14068-1 are particularly relevant for LCA practitioners, as they provide frameworks for quantifying and managing carbon footprints and climate neutrality claims.

1.2.1. EN ISO 14067 – CARBON FOOTPRINT OF PRODUCTS

EN ISO 14067, entitled "Greenhouse gases – Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification", specifies the principles, requirements, and guidelines for quantifying and reporting the carbon footprint of a product or CFP.

Key features of EN ISO 14067 include:

- **Scope and definitions:** The standard provides definitions for critical terms such as CFP, partial CFP, and Product Category Rules (PCRs), including those developed for seaweed (ISO TC 234 WG12) and farmed microalgae (ISO TC 234 WG15). These definitions are essential for ensuring clarity and consistency in algae LCAs.
- **Focus on climate change:** EN ISO 14067 is limited to a single impact category - climate change - and does not address other environmental, social, or economic aspects. It also excludes carbon offsetting and the communication of CFP information from its scope.
- **Applicability:** The standard is applicable to CFP studies and supports various applications, including regulatory compliance, marketing claims, and internal decision-making. However, it does not provide guidance on broader sustainability assessments.

1.2.2. EN ISO 14068-1 – CLIMATE CHANGE MANAGEMENT AND CARBON NEUTRALITY

EN ISO 14068-1, entitled "Climate change management - Transition to net zero - Part 1: Carbon neutrality", provides principles, requirements, and guidance for organisations and products aiming to achieve and demonstrate carbon neutrality. This standard emphasises a hierarchical approach to carbon management, prioritising: direct and indirect GHG emission reductions within the value chain, removal enhancements (e.g., carbon sequestration), and offsetting.

Key aspects of EN ISO 14068-1 include:

- **Carbon neutrality claims:** The standard outlines how to make credible carbon neutrality claims, ensuring they are scientifically valid, transparent, and verifiable. However, it does not describe how to perform an LCA, focusing instead on the management and communication of carbon neutrality efforts.
- **Support for sustainable development:** EN ISO 14068-1 is designed to support organisations committed to low GHG emission activities and sustainable development. It enhances the credibility of carbon neutrality claims and promotes science-based GHG reduction strategies.
- **Value chain approach:** The standard encourages a comprehensive life cycle and value chain perspective on carbon management, ensuring that efforts to achieve carbon neutrality are holistic and effective.

It is important to note that ISO 14068-1 is not an accounting guidance nor an LCA-specific standard. Instead, it focuses on requirements for reporting and claiming carbon neutrality.

1.3. INTEGRATION WITH BIO-BASED AND ALGAE-SPECIFIC STANDARDS

The application of EN ISO 14067:2018 and EN ISO 14068-1 in algae LCAs is strengthened when combined with bio-based and algae-specific standards, such as EN 16760, EN 18027, and EN 17983.

1.3.1. EN 16760 – LCA FOR BIO-BASED PRODUCTS

EN 16760 provides specific LCA requirements and guidance for bio-based products, including algae. It builds on EN ISO 14040 and 14044 and is designed to address the unique characteristics of bio-based systems, such as biogenic carbon accounting and land use impacts. While originally developed for terrestrial biomass (e.g., crops and forests), EN 16760 is also applicable to algae-based products, although it lacks algae-specific considerations, such as nutrient uptake from aquatic environments or closed-system cultivation. These limitations are addressed in newer standards such as EN 17983 and EN 18027.

EN 16760 can be applied to partial life cycle studies, such as cradle-to-gate or gate-to-gate analyses, provided that the scope and limitations are clearly justified. It also serves as a basis for assessing sustainability criteria outlined in EN 16751, which covers environmental, social, and economic dimensions of bio-based products.

1.3.2. EN 18027 - COMPARATIVE LCA FOR BIO-BASED AND FOSSIL-BASED PRODUCTS

EN 18027 provides additional requirements and guidelines for comparing bio-based products with their fossil-based equivalents (or counterparts), ensuring fair and balanced LCAs. This standard is particularly relevant for algae systems, as it addresses challenges such as:

- Functional equivalence between bio-based and fossil-based products.
- Biogenic vs. fossil carbon accounting, including the handling of carbon dioxide (CO₂) uptake and release.
- Data quality, end-of-life impacts, and land use considerations.

EN 18027 is critical for algae LCA practitioners, as it helps resolve discrepancies in comparative studies and ensures that algae systems are evaluated fairly against fossil-based alternatives. The standard's Annex A 1.1 specifically addresses carbon flows in algae grown with fossil CO₂, making it highly relevant for algae cultivation in closed-systems.

1.3.3. EN 17983 - ALGAE-SPECIFIC LCA REQUIREMENTS

EN 17983 is the first standard to provide algae-specific LCA requirements, focusing on the measurement of renewable algal raw materials for energy and non-energy applications. It builds on EN ISO 14040, EN ISO 14044, and EN 16760, offering:

- Algae-specific definitions and requirements for carbon accounting, nutrient flows, and energy/mass balances.

- Guidance on system boundaries, including the application of the "green box" approach for cradle-to-gate studies.
- Metrics for comparing algae systems with other biomass feedstocks, ensuring scientifically sound and transparent assessments.

EN 17983 is applicable to algae LCAs, excluding food and feed applications. It does not cover downstream processes such as biorefining, as these are considered equivalent to plant biomass processing. The standard is designed to be complementary to existing LCA frameworks, providing the tools needed to apply international standards to algae systems effectively.

TABLE 1

Summary of international and European standards relevant for life cycle assessment of algae systems.

The column "Application" indicates the type of product to which each standard applies. For algae-based products, the term "algae" refers to both microalgae and macroalgae unless otherwise specified. When a standard applies exclusively to microalgae or macroalgae, this is stated explicitly. For microalgae, if no cultivation mode is specified, the standard is assumed to cover photoautotrophic, mixotrophic, and heterotrophic cultivation. If a restriction applies, it is explicitly indicated.

CATEGORY	STANDARD	MAIN SCOPE	APPLICATION	SPECIFICITIES	REF.
Generic products	EN ISO 14040	Principles, framework, requirements and guidelines for LCA	All products and services	Establishes the foundation for all LCAs; defines terminology, phases and requirements; globally accepted	[1]
	EN ISO 14044	Requirements and guidelines for LCA	All products and services	Provides detailed procedural guidance for LCA phases, including goal and scope definition, LCI, LCIA and interpretation	[2]
	EN ISO 14046	Water footprint: principles, requirements and guidelines	Water footprint assessment	Focuses on water use and impacts, providing a framework for water footprint assessments	[3]
	EN ISO 14071	Critical review processes and reviewer competencies in LCA	Ensuring quality and credibility of LCA studies	Provides guidelines for conducting critical reviews and assessing reviewer competencies	[4]
	ISO 14075	Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA): principles and framework	Social dimension in LCA	Brings social/socio-economic criteria into LCA frameworks; supports evaluation of labour conditions, human rights, and community well-being	[5]
	EN ISO 14020	Environmental statements and programmes for products: Principles and general requirements	Umbrella standard for environmental labels	Establishes core principles for product-related environmental claims including self-declarations, ecolabels, EPDs and footprint communications;	[6]
	EN ISO 14021	Environmental labels and declarations: Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling)	All product type environmental labels and declarations	Sets requirements for verifiable self-declared environmental claims including symbols; prohibits vague claims; relies on claimant verification	[7]
	EN ISO 14024	Environmental labels and declarations: Type I environmental labelling - Principles and procedures	All product type environmental labels and declarations	Sets principles for developing Type I ecolabelling programmes; includes product category selection, environmental criteria, certification and compliance assessment	[8]
	EN ISO 14025	Environmental labels and declarations: Type III environmental declarations - Principles and procedures	All product type environmental labels and declarations	Specifies principles and requirements for Type III environmental declarations (EPDs) providing quantified environmental data	[9]
	CEN ISO/TS 14027	Development of product category rules (PCRs)	Environmental labels and declarations	Provides guidance for developing PCRs, ensuring consistency and comparability in LCAs	[10]

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TABLE 1 (continued)

CATEGORY	STANDARD	MAIN SCOPE	APPLICATION	SPECIFITIES	REF.
Generic products	ISO/TS 14029	Mutual recognition of environmental product declarations (EPDs) and footprint communication	Environmental statements and programs for products	Facilitates mutual recognition of EPDs and footprint communication programs	[11]
	EN ISO 14064-1	Greenhouse gases	GHG accounting and verification	Provides standards for quantifying, monitoring, reporting and verifying GHG emissions and removals	[12]
	EN ISO 14065	General principles and requirements for bodies validating and verifying environmental information	Broad sector application across all industries	Sector-specific application of ISO/IEC 17029; specifies competence, impartiality, consistent operation requirements for bodies validating and verifying environmental information	[13]
	ISO 14066	Environmental information: Competence requirements for teams validating and verifying environmental information	Broad sector application across all industries	Specifies competence criteria for validation/verification teams and independent reviewers for environmental information; applicable to all organisations conducting validations, verifications, and agreed-upon procedures	[14]
	EN ISO 14067	Carbon footprint of products; quantification and reporting requirements	Product-level greenhouse gas (carbon) assessment	Focuses solely on climate change impact, aligns with ISO 14040/44 methodologies	[15]
	EN ISO 14068-1	Climate change management; transition to net zero: carbon neutrality	Corporate/product-level net zero claims	Sets requirements for achieving and demonstrating carbon neutrality; prioritises emission reductions and removal enhancements over offsetting	[16]
	ISO 59020	Circular economy: Measuring and assessing circularity performance	Cross-sector circularity assessment	Provides metrics and methods to quantify and evaluate circularity performance of products and systems	[17]
	ISO 59014	Environmental management and circular economy: Sustainability and traceability of the recovery of secondary materials - Principles, requirements and guidance.	Recovery and recycling operations	Establishes principles, requirements and guidance for sustainable and traceable recovery of secondary materials	[18]
Bio-based products	EN 16760	LCA for bio-based products	Bio-based products, including algae	Adds biobased-specific LCA guidance to ISO 14040/44, bridges land and aquatic biomass	[19]
	EN 16751	Sustainability criteria for bio-based products	Any bio-based product	Sets environmental, social and economic sustainability criteria for bio-based products	[20]
	ISO 13065	Sustainability criteria for bioenergy	Biomass for energy, including algae	Focuses on broader sustainability: environmental, social, economic for bioenergy value chains	[21]
	EN 18027	Comparative assessment of bio-based vs fossil-based products	Comparing bio-based to fossil-based	Provides extra guidance for fair comparisons and "functional equivalence" in LCA	[22]
Algae-based products	EN 17983	Measurement of renewable algal raw material for energy /non-energy applications	Algae/microalgae raw material LCA (non food applications)	Algae-specific LCA metrics and guidance, focus on carbon and nutrient flows, cradle-to-gate boundary	[23]
	ISO 20423	Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for calculating carbon footprint of farmed macroalgae	Macroalgae aquaculture value chains; seedling production to consumption	Aligns with international LCA standards; enables consistent carbon footprint claims; not for full sustainability assessment	[24]
	ISO/DIS 25250 (under development)	Terms, methods, and analysis for carbon fixation rate in farmed macroalgae	Measurement in farmed macroalgae	Specifies harmonised sampling, analytical, and calculation procedures; supports robust carbon data in LCAs	[25]

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TABLE 1 (continued)

CATEGORY	STANDARD	MAIN SCOPE	APPLICATION	SPECIFICITIES	REF.
Algae-based products	ISO/AWI 25783 (under development)	Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for carbon footprint of farmed photosynthetic microalgae	Microalgae aquaculture value chains; seedling production to consumption	Mirrors ISO 20423 for microalgae; enables consistent carbon footprint reporting for photosynthetic microalgal products	[26]
	ISO/AWI 25782 (under development)	Terms, determination rules and methods for carbon sequestration rate in farmed photosynthetic microalgae	Measurement in farmed microalgae	Defines and standardises procedures for quantifying carbon sequestration by microalgae; critical for climate impact studies	[27]

2. COMPLEMENTARY GUIDELINES AND FRAMEWORKS FOR ALGAE LCAs

In addition to formal standards, various technical guidance documents play a critical role in supporting consistent, robust, and contextually relevant LCA work, particularly in the rapidly evolving algal sector. These documents provide detailed operational guidance, methodological frameworks, and best practices that complement international and European standards. Table 2 summarises the major international guidance documents relevant for LCAs of algae systems.

2.1. GENERAL METHODOLOGICAL GUIDELINES

2.1.1. INTERNATIONAL REFERENCE LIFE CYCLE DATA SYSTEM HANDBOOK

Developed by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (EC JRC), the ILCD Handbook is a cornerstone for LCA methodology. While not a formal standard, it is widely recognised as a foundational guide for conducting robust and contextually relevant LCAs. It provides detailed, step-by-step guidance for implementing ISO 14040 and 14044 requirements across all LCA phases, including system definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and reporting. The handbook fosters methodological harmonisation, enhances consistency across LCA studies, and promotes alignment with EU databases and policies such as the Product Environmental Footprint. Although supplementary to formal standards, the ILCD Handbook remains indispensable for state-of-the-art LCA work, especially in innovative sectors such as the algal industry.

2.1.2. UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME GUIDELINES FOR SOCIAL LCA

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) “Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)”, developed in collaboration with the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC), integrate social and socio-economic considerations into LCA. These guidelines enable practitioners to assess impacts on diverse stakeholder groups, including workers, communities, and consumers. The latest revision aligns with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), supporting holistic and inclusive social sustainability assessments.

2.1.3. PRODUCT ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT GUIDE

The European Commission’s Product Environmental Footprint Guide is an ambitious effort to standardise multi-impact environmental assessments at the product level. Through Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs), it enables comparability across sectors and product groups, aligning with EU sustainability objectives. The guide is increasingly shaping policy and practice within the EU and beyond, making it critical for comprehensive LCA work in emerging sectors, including algae.

2.1.4. PRODUCT CATEGORY RULES

Product Category Rules provide detailed, product category-specific methodological requirements that clarify how LCAs are conducted within a defined category. PCRs specify system boundaries, data quality criteria, allocation rules, and life cycle stages to ensure that environmental assessments and resulting declarations are consistent, comparable, and reliable among products in the same category. They serve as operational frameworks bridging broad LCA standards and the practical development of EPDs.

2.1.5. ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT DECLARATIONS

Environmental Product Declarations are third-party verified documents that transparently communicate the environmental performance of products based on PCR-compliant LCAs. EPDs are often registered with recognised programs (e.g., EPD International), enabling stakeholders, including consumers, regulators, and businesses, to access comparable and verifiable environmental information in publicly accessible online registries. They complement the PEF and PCR frameworks by providing practical tools for environmental claims, compliance, and market transparency.

In addition, region-specific guidelines and frameworks play an important role in adapting LCA methodologies to local regulatory, environmental, and market contexts. Examples include France’s BPX 30-323 standard, Japan’s EcoLeaf program, and the Korean Carbon Footprint of Products/Environmental Product Declaration program. These initiatives help ensure that LCA practices remain relevant to regional priorities while supporting comparability across borders.

2.2. GUIDELINES FOR GREENHOUSE GAS ACCOUNTING AND CARBON FOOTPRINTING

2.2.1. PUBLICLY AVAILABLE SPECIFICATION 2050

Developed by the British Standards Institution (BSI), PAS 2050 offers a standardised method for quantifying the life cycle GHG emissions of goods and services. It is widely used for product carbon footprinting, ensuring consistency, transparency, and comparability in climate change impact assessments by defining system boundaries, data sources, allocation, and reporting rules.

2.2.2. GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS PROTOCOL

The GHG Protocol Product Life Cycle Accounting and Reporting Standard is a globally recognised framework developed by the World Resources Institute (WRI) and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). It provides detailed guidance to quantify, report, and manage GHG emissions over product life cycles. It promotes harmonisation of system boundaries, data requirements, and calculation methods, fostering comparability and transparency across supply chains. Modular in design, the standard enables focused assessments of life cycle stages or impacts and supports improved product design and consumer communication of environmental impacts.

In addition to accounting and footprinting guidelines, several initiatives guide organisations in using emission data to set climate goals. For example, the Science-Based Targets initiative (SBTi) Corporate Net-Zero Standard offers guidance on establishing science-aligned near- and long-term emission reduction targets.

2.2.3. SCIENCE-BASED TARGETS INITIATIVE CORPORATE NET ZERO STANDARD

The Science-Based Targets initiative Corporate Net-Zero Standard provides companies with clear, science-aligned guidance to set near-term and long-term net-zero GHG emission targets. The Net Zero Standard emphasises prioritising emission reductions before carbon removal or offsetting, ensuring transparency and accountability aligned with the 1.5°C global warming limit. It supports organisational climate leadership and credible net-zero commitments.

2.3. GUIDELINES FOR CARBON CAPTURE, STORAGE AND UTILISATION

2.3.1. INSIGHTS FROM MORE GENERAL FRAMEWORKS

Specific guidelines are essential to address the unique methodological challenges of carbon capture and utilisation in algae-based systems, complementing broad frameworks such as the ILCD Handbook, GHG Protocol, and the EU's QU.A.L.I.TY criteria. While these offer important carbon accounting and verification guidance, sector-specific challenges in algae LCAs require tailored approaches.

The ILCD Handbook provides detailed carbon accounting methods to distinguish biogenic from fossil carbon and to define system boundaries including CO₂ uptake and end-of-life emissions. The GHG Protocol adds harmonised rules for quantifying and reporting GHG emissions across global supply chains. The QU.A.L.I.TY criteria ensure carbon removals are verifiable, durable, and sustainable, aligned with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) monitoring, reporting, and verification requirements.

It is important to note that standards such as ISO 14064 provide a framework for carbon offsetting and crediting market mechanisms, enabling algae-based carbon capture projects to access economic incentives under transparent and credible conditions.

2.3.2. GUIDELINES FOR LCA OF CARBON CAPTURE AND UTILISATION

LCA4CCU provides a harmonised framework for assessing the environmental impacts of carbon capture and utilisation technologies, focusing on the full life cycle from CO₂ capture through conversion into products as well as their use and disposal. By defining consistent system boundaries, methodological assumptions, and reporting requirements, LCA4CCU improves comparability and transparency of CCU LCAs. It addresses challenges such as accounting for CO₂ as a feedstock, energy demands, and variable carbon storage durations, supporting reliable evaluation of CCU's potential climate benefits and trade-offs. It provides a robust methodological framework that can be adapted to assess algae-based carbon capture and utilisation systems, facilitating consistent and comprehensive environmental evaluation despite not being algae-specific.

2.3.3. VOLUNTARY CARBON MARKET METHODS FOR ALGAE-BASED SYSTEMS

Several voluntary carbon market methodologies provide frameworks for certifying algae-based carbon capture projects. Among these is the **Puro Microalgae Carbon Fixation and Sinking** (MCFS) methodology, which specifically targets CO₂ dissolved in seawater. This process enhances microalgae growth on engineered substrates that are then rapidly sunk into deep ocean waters, ensuring long-term carbon storage with a minimum durability of 200 years. To safeguard environmental integrity, the MCFS methodology enforces strict site eligibility, rigorous monitoring, and a capped scale per facility. Certification is facilitated through Puro.earth's transparent CO₂ Removal Certificates, offering a pathway for oceanic algae-based carbon sequestration.

The **Japan Blue Credit** (J-Blue Credit) is a pioneering voluntary carbon credit scheme focused specifically on blue carbon projects, including seagrass, seaweed beds, mangroves, and tidal flats within Japan's coastal areas. The program quantifies and verifies CO₂ removal achieved through ecosystem restoration, maintenance, and creation activities following rigorous methods for surveying, calculating removal coefficients, and ensuring additionality and permanence. Certified credits are issued annually based on verified net carbon removals and managed through an online credit management system. J-Blue Credit emphasises local stakeholder involvement, environmental integrity, and adaptive management, and is recognised under Japan's GHG regulatory frameworks, including eligibility for Japan's emissions trading system. This initiative exemplifies regionally adapted carbon market methods advancing algae-related blue carbon sequestration.

TABLE 2

Summary of major international, European, and regional guidelines and frameworks relevant for life cycle assessment of algae systems.

Document / Organisation	Main aspect covered	Year	Reference
ILCD Handbook, European Commission Joint Research Center	Comprehensive operational guidance for conducting environmental LCAs, covering goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation, with a focus on methodological harmonisation across EU studies.	2010-2011	[28]
Guidelines for Social LCA, UNEP/SETAC	Methodological guidance for assessing social and socio-economic impacts of product life cycles, including stakeholder impacts, impact pathways, relevant indicators, and supply chain data collection, aligned with SDGs.	2020	[29]
Product Environmental Footprint (PEF), European Commission	Methodology for multi-impact environmental footprint calculation of products, beyond climate change, with rules for sectoral PEF Category Rules (PEFCRs).	2013, 2021	[30]
Product Category Rules (PCRs)	Specific guidelines that define consistent rules for conducting LCAs within product categories, covering system boundaries, data quality, allocation, and reporting. PCRs ensure comparable and transparent environmental assessments and enable the development of Environmental Product Declarations.	-	-
Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs)	Verified documents based on PCR-compliant LCAs that communicate products' environmental footprints transparently. EPDs support informed decision-making by providing consistent, comparable, third-party validated environmental information.	-	-
PAS 2050, British Standards Institution	Standardised method for quantifying product life cycle GHG emissions (carbon footprint), with rules for system boundaries, data sources, allocation, and reporting.	2008 (rev. 2011)	[31]
GHG Protocol, WRI/WBCSD	Global guidance for quantifying and reporting product carbon footprints, focusing on boundary-setting, data requirements, calculations and value chain engagement.	2011	[32]
Corporate Net-Zero Standard, Science-Based Target initiative (SBTi)	Guidance for setting science-aligned, near, and long-term, net-zero GHG emission targets, emphasising emission reductions before offsetting, aligned with 1.5°C pathways.	2022	[33]
LCA4CCU, European Commission Joint Research Center	Methodological guidance for life cycle assessment studies of carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) technologies, supporting comprehensive environmental evaluation.	2022	[34]
Puro Microalgae Carbon Fixation and Sinking	Certification for microalgae-based ocean CO ₂ sequestration, involving environmental safeguards, monitoring, and verification.	2025	[35]
Japan Blue Credit	Regional scheme certifying marine blue carbon projects, with verification protocols, stakeholder involvement and recognition under Japan's regulations.	2025	[36]
Verra standards	Set of protocols for various carbon sequestration approaches, lacking algae-specific standards, with complexities in project comparability.	2025	[37, 38]
Gold Standard	Certification principles emphasising climate integrity, environmental, and social aspects, adaptable for emerging and algae-related carbon removal methods.	2025	[39]
BSI Flex	Supportive framework for quantifying and verifying GHG removals in bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), adaptable for algae-based processes.	2025	[40]

In comparison, **Verra's standards** encompass various carbon capture approaches, such as biochar utilisation and other carbon storage methods, although they currently lack algae-specific protocols. This diversity in method definitions and retention time requirements raises challenges for directly comparing or evaluating algae-based carbon projects certified under different Verra methodologies.

Similarly, the **Gold Standard** offers well-established criteria for engineered carbon removal solutions, focusing on environmental and social integrity but has yet to introduce algae-specific standards. This gap emphasises the sector's need for harmonised certification frameworks tailored to algae.

Finally, the **BSI Flex 2006 v1.0** standard supports rigorous quantification and verification of GHG removals in bioenergy

with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) projects. Its adaptable framework is suitable for application in algae-based carbon removal efforts, promoting consistency and integrity across diverse operational contexts.

3. PAST & ONGOING INITIATIVES RELEVANT TO ALGAE LCAs

A variety of past and ongoing initiatives are contributing to the harmonisation and advancement of LCA methodologies, particularly in the algae sector. These initiatives focus on sector-specific challenges, biogenic carbon modelling, data quality, and methodological alignment across industries (Table 3).

TABLE 3

Summary of past and ongoing initiatives relevant for life cycle assessment of algae systems (non-exhaustive list).

Focus	Name	Main aspect covered	Reference
Chemicals	Together For Sustainability initiative (TFS)	Collaboration among chemical industry leaders aimed at improving sustainability performance across the supply chain. TFS focuses on standardising sustainability assessments, including LCA practices, to enhance transparency, data quality, and comparability in the chemical sector.	[41]
Biogenic carbon	Life Cycle Initiative on biogenic carbon	Addresses the unique challenges of accounting for biogenic carbon in LCA studies. It provides methodological guidance for assessing the carbon sequestration, storage, and emissions associated with bio-based materials, including algae. The initiative aims to harmonise approaches for biogenic carbon accounting to improve consistency and comparability in LCA results.	[42]
Carbon utilisation	Global CO ₂ Initiative /University of Michigan	Advances technologies and methodologies for carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS). The initiative supports research, policy development, and standardisation to accelerate the commercialisation of carbon-based products, including those derived from algae. It provides resources, case studies, and best practices for integrating CCUS into LCA frameworks.	[43]
Bio-based industry	EU-funded ALIGNED project	Harmonises LCA methodologies across different bio-based sectors, including algae systems. The project focuses on aligning data, methods, and tools to improve the consistency, reliability, and comparability of LCA studies. It supports the development of sector-specific guidelines and promotes interoperability among LCA databases and software.	[44]
Bio-based industry	EU-funded LCA4BIO project	Focuses on LCA for bio-based products, including algae. It provides guidance and tools for assessing the environmental impacts of bio-based materials, with a focus on greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sequestration, and sustainability metrics. The initiative aligns with the GHG Protocol's Land Sector and Removals Guidance, ensuring consistent and transparent accounting of biogenic carbon in LCA studies.	[45]
General LCA support /Food systems	European Platform on LCA	Provides comprehensive resources, tools, and databases to support and harmonise LCA activities across multiple sectors, including sustainable food systems. It facilitates data sharing, methodological alignment, and best practice dissemination, underpinning EU policy goals such as the Farm to Fork Strategy. EPLCA supports the development of innovative simulation models and extensive sustainability monitoring frameworks focused on the full food supply chain, enabling policy-relevant, interdisciplinary environmental assessments.	[46]

4. CONCLUSIONS

LCA remains the cornerstone for evaluating the environmental sustainability of algae-based products and systems. The integration of internationally recognised standards such as EN ISO 14040 and 14044, complemented by algae-specific standards and sector-focused initiatives, ensures methodological robustness and facilitates comparability across studies (Figure 2 and Table 4). Despite significant progress, challenges persist due to the diversity of standards and the evolving nature of algae technologies underscoring the need for ongoing harmonisation and development of algae-specific guidance.

Methodological frameworks and voluntary carbon certification schemes including LCA4CCU, Puro’s Microalgae methodology, Verra, Gold Standard, and BSI Flex 2006, provide essential tools for quantifying carbon capture and utilisation, each with specific scopes and strengths. Their collective advancement promotes transparency and market confidence, although further alignment is crucial to enhance applicability and comparability, especially in algae-based carbon removal.

Region-specific frameworks underscore the importance of tailoring LCA approaches to local regulatory and market conditions while ensuring cross-border consistency. Practitioners are encouraged to apply core international, sector-specific, and application-specific standards, together with the most relevant guidelines to produce scientifically relevant and meaningful LCAs that support informed decision-making in both industry and policy contexts.

Overall, this information paper serves as a foundational guide for selecting and applying the most relevant LCA standards and guidelines for algae systems, supporting the sector’s sustainable growth and its meaningful contribution to mitigating environmental impacts.

Fig.2 - Summary of standards, guidelines, and initiatives relevant to conduct more transparent, reproducible, and comparable life cycle assessment studies of algae-based products.

TABLE 4

Topical coverage of standards, guidelines, and initiatives relevant to life cycle assessment of algae systems.

The table illustrates how standards, guidelines, and initiatives complement each other across five key categories: foundational, thematic, sector-specific, communication, and harmonisation. Filled circles (●) indicate primary relevance, hollow circles (○) indicate secondary or partial relevance, and dashes (–) indicate no relevance to the category.

STANDARDS	FOUNDATIONAL	THEMATIC	SECTOR-SPECIFIC	COMMUNICATION	HARMONISATION
EN ISO 14040	●	–	–	○	○
EN ISO 14044	●	–	–	○	○
EN ISO 14046	○	● (water footprint)	–	–	○
ISO 14075	○	● (social LCA)	–	–	○
ISO 59020	○	● (circular economy)	–	–	○
ISO 59014	○	● (circular economy)	–	–	○
EN ISO 14064-1	○	● (GHG)	–	–	○
EN ISO 14067	○	● (carbon footprint)	–	–	○
EN ISO 14068-1	○	● (climate neutrality)	–	–	○
ISO 14071	–	–	–	● (critical reviews)	–
EN ISO 14020–25 series	–	–	–	● (labels & decl.)	–
CEN ISO/TS 14027	–	–	–	● (PCR rules)	–
ISO/TS 14029	–	–	–	● (EPD/Footprints)	–
EN ISO 14065	–	–	–	● (verification)	–
ISO 14066	–	–	–	● (verification)	–
EN 16760	○	–	● (biobased)	–	○
EN 16751	–	–	● (biobased)	–	○
ISO 13065	–	–	● (bioenergy)	–	○
EN 18027	–	–	● (biobased vs. fossil)	–	○
EN 17983	–	–	● (algae, non-food)	–	○
ISO 20423	–	○ (carbon footprint)	● (macroalgae)	–	○
ISO/DIS 25250	–	○ (carbon fixation)	● (macroalgae)	–	○
ISO/AWI 25783	–	○ (carbon footprint PCR)	● (microalgae)	–	○
ISO/AWI 25782	–	○ (carbon sequestration)	● (microalgae)	–	○
GUIDELINES	FOUNDATIONAL	THEMATIC	SECTOR-SPECIFIC	COMMUNICATION	HARMONISATION
ILCD Handbook	●	○	–	○	–
UNEP S-LCA	○	● (social LCA)	–	–	○
PEF guide	–	● (LCIA, PEFCRs)	–	○	○
PCRs	–	–	● (per sector)	○	○
EPDs	–	–	● (per sector)	○	○

Table continues on the next page

TABLE 4 (continued)

GUIDELINES	FOUNDATIONAL	THEMATIC	SECTOR-SPECIFIC	COMMUNICATION	HARMONISATION
GHG protocol	–	● (GHG)	–	–	○
SBTi Net-Zero	–	● (GHG)	–	○	○
LCA4CCU	–	● (CCU)	–	○	○
GUIDELINES	–	–	–	–	–
Puro Microalgae	–	○ (CCU)	● (microalgae)	○	○
Japan Blue Credit	–	● (CCU)	○ (blue bioeconomy)	○	○
Verra standards	–	● (incl. CCU)	–	○	○
Gold Standard	–	● (incl. CCU)	–	○	○
BSI Flex	–	● (incl. CCU)	–	–	○
INITIATIVES	–	–	–	–	–
TFS	–	–	● (chemicals)	–	○
LCI biogenic carbon	–	● (biogenic carbon)	–	–	○
Global CO2 initiative	–	● (CCU)	–	–	–
ALIGNED	–	–	● (biobased)	–	○
LCA4BIO	–	–	● (biobased)	–	○
European platform LCA	–	–	● (incl. food systems)	–	–

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